

Orientation Dependent Interlayer Coupling in Organic-Inorganic Heterostructures

Cian Bartlam,¹ Nihit Saigal,² Stefan Heiserer,¹ Hendrik Lambers,² Ursula Wurstbauer,^{2,3} Georg S. Duesberg^{1*}

¹Institute of Physics EIT 2, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology, & Center for Integrated Sensors, University of the Bundeswehr Munich, 85579 Neubiberg, Germany

²Institute of Physics, University of Münster, 48149 Münster, Germany

³Center for Soft Nanoscience (SoN), University of Münster, 48149 Münster, Germany

*duesberg@unibw.de

Abstract:

Organic-inorganic two-dimensional heterostructures combine the high optical absorption of organic molecules with exciton dominated optical properties in layered transition metal dichalcogenides such as MoS₂. Critical to the interaction and the optical response in such hybrid systems is the electronic band alignment at the interface between the two species. Here we investigate the coupling of monolayers of perylene derivatives with bilayer MoS₂. In particular, we identify variation in the perylene orientation on the MoS₂ surface using Raman spectroscopy and scanning probe microscopy. Low temperature optical spectroscopy reveals orientation dependent interlayer exciton formation. Furthermore, power dependent photoluminescence measurements provide insight into the modified interlayer charge transfer in these heterostructures. We find a saturation of interlayer states under high excitation power when the perylene molecules are in a perpendicular orientation to the surface which leads to electron accumulation in the MoS₂, whereas parallel alignment of the perylene molecules leads to enhanced populations of organic-inorganic interlayer excitons. This work provides insights into the optimization of organic-inorganic heterostructures, with particular relevance to applications for optoelectronic and excitonic devices.

Keywords:

Heterostructures, interlayer excitons, charge transfer, perylene, MoS₂, self-assembly, photoluminescence

Introduction:

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have emerged as candidates for next generation optical devices, hosting a range of novel optoelectronic properties even at room temperature.¹⁻³ A general feature of these systems is the hosting of excitonic states with high binding energies which, through type-II band alignment with other layers, can result in spatial separation of charge carriers by charge transfer (CT).⁴ Artificially stacking TMD layers, offers a way to modulate these properties, such as the control of interlayer (IL) excitons with characteristic low energy features in their emission spectra.^{5,6} Current challenges for TMD-TMD heterostructures include the strong dependencies of IL excitons on stacking

alignment/twist angle⁷ and variations in IL coupling in the presence of contamination⁸ leading to extrinsically mediated recombination.⁹

Organic semiconductors, such as perylene derivatives, have been shown to noncovalently interact with group VI TMDs, resulting in organic-inorganic heterostructures that modulate the electronic and optical properties of the 2D material.¹⁰⁻¹³ Properties of those systems include increased photocurrent generation due to higher charge carrier separation, doping via CT, and the quenching or enhancement of photoluminescence depending on the band alignment. This is in turn dependent on both the structure and conformation of the adsorbed molecular derivative.^{14,15} This dependence allows a high level of tunability of the heterostructure. While hybridization and the formation of CT excitons between TMDs and organic molecules has been proposed,^{16,17} upon photoexcitation competing CT mechanisms result in a combination of either free carrier generation upon Dexter-type CT or the formation of IL bound excitons.¹⁸ Differences in band bending at the interface when comparing TMD monolayers to bulk crystals has been shown to generate free charge carriers in the monolayer case, whereas IL excitons form in the bulk,¹⁹ allowing a combination of these phenomena to be studied in few layer and bilayer TMDs coupled to organic molecules. Understanding the interaction at the interface of these organic-inorganic heterostructures is therefore crucial to the understanding of CT mechanisms in these systems.²⁰

Here we report on the optical properties of well-defined organic-inorganic heterostructures from perylene bisimide (PBI) derivatives on bilayer MoS₂ produced via deposition of the PBI molecules in liquid on mechanically exfoliated MoS₂. We identify the spectral features at both ambient and cryogenic temperatures that are due to variation in the molecular orientation of PBI on the surface of the 2D material. We show that PBI-bilayer MoS₂ systems with a high degree of orbital alignment can host IL excitons and that conversely poor orbital alignment results in reduced IL excitonic photoluminescence and decreased CT upon photoexcitation, highlighting the importance of molecular alignment of the organic layer at the interface.

Results & Discussion:

Room Temperature Raman, Photoluminescence and AFM analysis:

Figure 1 (a) Functionalization scheme, structure of the PBI and optical micrograph of a functionalized bilayer MoS₂, 20 μm scale; (b) RT PL spectra of unfunctionalized 2L MoS₂, and different regions of PBI functionalized 2L MoS₂, denoted as PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 normalized to the MoS₂ A_{1g} Raman mode at 532nm excitation, red box highlights the frequency region of the PBI Raman modes; (c) Intensity map of the highlighted components of the Raman spectra shown in (b), showing distinct domains in green and blue corresponding to PBI-R1 and PBI-R2, respectively. 5 μm scale; Dashed box shows the position of the AFM image shown in (e), 5 μm scale; (d) High resolution Raman spectra of 2L MoS₂, PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 at 532 nm excitation at RT, red box highlights the PBI and MoS₂ LA(M) Raman modes. Inset – low frequency and E²_{2g} regions of the Raman spectra; (e) AFM topographic image of the PBI-functionalized flake shown in 1c. The two domains of the PBI R1 and R2 in light and dark blue are visible, the borderline having

the same shape as in the Raman in 1c. The dashed line shows the line profile shown in Inset, with a clearly visible step at the interface between the two domains, 2 μm scale. (b),(d) are vertically displaced for clarity.

In Figure 1(a) the workflow for the assembly of the MoS₂-PBI heterostructures is depicted. In short, bilayer (2L) MoS₂ flakes were first micromechanically cleaved and transferred onto 70 nm thermally grown SiO₂/Si substrates. The layer number was determined using optical microscopy and low frequency Raman spectroscopy.²¹ 2L MoS₂ was then functionalized by liquid phase deposition of PBI with a derivative which is soluble in organic solvents as detailed in the Methods section. As a result the PBI selectively assembles onto TMDs as a monolayer as shown previously.²²

Photoluminescence (PL) and Raman measurements at room temperature (RT – 294 K, 532 nm) on a 2L MoS₂ flake before and after functionalization are shown in Figure 1(b and d). The pristine MoS₂ spectrum, labelled 2L MoS₂, shows broad A and B exciton PL at 1.9 eV ($\sim 3800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 2.1 eV ($\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$), respectively. After functionalization, the PL of the MoS₂ is significantly quenched across the heterostructure. However, the quenching is markedly different in distinct regions of the MoS₂ flake, denoted as PBI-R1 (green spectrum) and PBI-R2 (blue spectrum) with the spatial distribution of these areas is highlighted in the Raman map shown in Figure 1(c). For PBI-R2, both A and B exciton peaks show a reduction in intensity, while the A exciton spectral region shows higher quenching relative to the B exciton region in PBI-R1. Interestingly, the indirect PL intensity between 6000-7000 cm^{-1} (~ 1.4 -1.6 eV) is similar for pristine 2L MoS₂ and PBI-R2 but is almost completely quenched in PBI-R1.

A strong perylene signature can be seen in the Raman spectrum in PBI-R1 region (Figure 1(b)). The modes at ~ 1301 , 1383 and 1587 cm^{-1} are assigned to the ring-breathing, Kekule and asymmetric modes of the polyaromatic perylene core²³ and emerge due to resonant exciton-phonon coupling and CT between the perylene molecules and the TMD.^{14,24} The spectrum of PBI-R1 also shows additional modes at 235 and 290 cm^{-1} , highlighted in red in Figure 1(d), which are assigned to the MoS₂ LA(M) mode and a PBI A_g mode originating from the perylene core,²⁵ respectively. The presence of the LA(M) mode indicates disorder-induced scattering²⁶ where perylene molecules are expected to hybridize with MoS₂ layers at this symmetry point.¹⁷

AFM topographic imaging of the 2L MoS₂-PBI heterostructure, shown in Figure 1(e), shows a clear contrast between the PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 regions identified in the Raman map of Figure 1(c). The step height from the underlying substrate to the heterostructure, averaged over 50 lines, is measured to be 3.0 ± 0.2 nm for PBI-R1 and 3.8 ± 0.2 nm for PBI-R2. This clearly indicates a different arrangement of the perylene derivatives in the respective regions. Ambient AFM of MoS₂ bilayers typically gives thicknesses ranging from 1.4-1.6 nm.²⁷ After subtraction, we then calculate an average PBI layer thickness in the range of 1.4-1.6 nm for PBI-R1 and 2.2-2.4 nm for PBI-R2, where PBI-R2 has a similar step height observed for self-aggregated perylene derivatives.²⁸

Figure 2 Statistical analysis of MoS₂ Raman modes of the PBI-MoS₂ heterostructure shown in Figure 1 (dashed lines, Gaussian fits): (a) Histogram showing the frequency distribution of the E¹_{2g} mode; (b) Histogram showing the FWHM distribution of the E¹_{2g} mode; (c) Spatial maps of the E¹_{2g} frequency (above) and FWHM (below); (d) Histogram showing the frequency distribution of the E²_{2g} mode; (e) Histogram showing the FWHM distribution of the E²_{2g} mode; (f) Spatial maps of the E²_{2g} frequency (above) and FWHM (below); (g) Histogram showing the frequency distribution of the B²_{2g} mode; (h) Histogram showing the FWHM distribution of the B²_{2g} mode; (i) Spatial maps of the B²_{2g} frequency (above) and FWHM (below).

After functionalization with PBI, the in-plane E¹_{2g} and out-of-plane A_{1g} Raman modes of MoS₂ (Figure 1(d)) were fitted with Lorentzian functions over an area of the heterostructure. After statistical analysis of the spectral data (Figure 2), the E¹_{2g} mode in PBI-R1 shows a slight broadening with an increase in full width half maximum (FWHM) of 0.4 ± 0.2 cm⁻¹ when compared to PBI-R2, indicating the presence of higher strain in the MoS₂ lattice in this region.^{29,30} In addition, the E¹_{2g} mode frequency in PBI-R1 is blueshifted by 0.3 ± 0.1 cm⁻¹, which further indicates higher lattice strain. We do not observe any significant change in the A_{1g} frequency or width between regions. The difference in the low frequency MoS₂ Raman modes (Figure 2 (d-i)) also shows a change in environment, where the E²_{2g} in-plane shear

mode at 22.8 cm^{-1} shows broadening of $0.8 \pm 0.4\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a blueshift of $0.8 \pm 0.1\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in PBI-R1. The out-of-plane B_{2g}^2 interlayer mode centered at 41 cm^{-1} does not show any significant frequency shift between regions but shows a large increase in FWHM from approximately 19 to 36 cm^{-1} . It is likely that there is an additional contribution from the PBI molecule in this range resulting in the observed broadening, due to an enhancement of out-of-plane perylene Raman modes at this frequency.²⁵

The reduction in the MoS_2 A exciton emission intensity at RT, combined with the lack of a PBI Raman signature shows the presence of coupling between the PBI molecule and the MoS_2 orbitals in PBI-R2 but to a lesser degree than in the assembly of PBI-R1. This effect has been shown in coupled organic molecule-graphene heterostructures^{31,32} where molecular symmetry was found to contribute to the Raman enhancement effect³³ and is sensitive to molecular orientation.³⁴ Low temperature MoS_2 resonant Raman measurements at 632 nm excitation were performed and the 290 cm^{-1} A_g perylene mode has a reduced intensity in PBI-R1, as to be expected for this Raman enhancement mechanism, away from resonance with the perylene absorption.²⁴ PBI-R2 shows the presence of this mode under these conditions, indicating higher levels of intermolecular interaction³⁵ (see S1, Supporting Information for further discussion). These observations support there being two different orientations of the PBI molecules on the MoS_2 surface for the PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 regions. The emergence of the LA(M) Raman mode in the PBI-R1 Raman spectrum (RT, 532 nm , Figure 1(d)) is likely from greater PBI- MoS_2 orbital overlap in this region through parallel alignment of the PBI molecules to the TMD surface, and further evidencing intermolecular interaction. This would account for the strain-induced changes observed in the in-plane E_{2g}^1 and E_{2g}^2 Raman modes (Figure 2), due to a mismatch between the PBI ordering and the MoS_2 lattice as has been reported for TMD-graphene heterostructures.³⁶

The AFM height difference between the two regions is below that of a monolayer, *i.e.* not additive. It indicates that the variation in PBI orientation on the MoS_2 crystal plane, is the origin of the observed PBI Raman signal enhancement and lattice strain in the MoS_2 bilayer. The AFM measurements suggest that the perylene molecules in PBI-R2 are arranged perpendicular to the surface as has been observed previously for PBI derivatives on graphene.³⁷ Perylene molecules have been shown to have a range of conformations when assembled from solution^{38,39} and similar perylene bisimides have been shown to organize either parallel⁴⁰ or perpendicular to 2D surfaces with tilt angles ranging from 12° - 62° .⁴¹⁻⁴³ The cleanliness of the 2D interface prior to functionalisation is often critical to molecular assembly, as highlighted elsewhere²⁰ and surface contamination has been shown to affect organic packing on 2D materials resulting in changes in orientation.⁴⁴ The occurrence of the PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 phases is tentatively attributed to contamination on the MoS_2 surface, prior to functionalization. MoS_2 crystals that were functionalized immediately after exfoliation exclusively show the PBI-R1 conformation with planar arrangement of the PDI molecules (S2, Supporting Information). Further investigating the assembly mechanism may open a pathway for the controlled generation of different molecular arrangement on 2D surfaces.

Low Temperature Photoluminescence Spectroscopy

Figure 3 (a) Steady state PL spectra of unfunctionalized 2L MoS₂, PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 (532 nm excitation wavelength, 1 μ W power, temperature 4 K) with schematics of the different orientations of the PBI layer; (b) Spectral fitting and components of the momentum indirect region (1.3-1.6 eV) of the PL spectra shown in (a); (c) Spectral fitting and components of the momentum direct region (1.8-1.95 eV) of the PL spectra shown in (a); (d) Schematic band diagram of PBI-functionalized bilayer MoS₂ showing the type-II alignment of the heterostructure and the location of electron-hole pairs. All plots are vertically displaced and the intensities of (b) and (c) are normalized for clarity.

To further investigate the effect of the PBI orientation on the optical properties of the heterostructure, low temperature PL spectroscopy was performed. The 2L MoS₂ measured here exhibits a similar Raman and PL spectrum at RT to the unfunctionalized bilayer described above. Figure 3(a) shows low temperature PL spectra (4 K) acquired at 1 μ W excitation power under 532 nm illumination. The most striking differences between the spectra of 2L MoS₂ and PBI-R1, PBI-R2 is the quenching of the higher energy direct exciton emissions even more pronounced than at room-temperature and the large increase in peak intensity between 1.3-1.6 eV, with the emergence of a low energy feature at 1.39-1.4 eV. The suppression of the direct emission after PBI functionalisation is likely related to the CT between PBI and MoS₂ due to type-II band alignment at the heterostructure interface. Conversely, we attribute the large increase in the lower energy luminescence to suppression of nonradiative recombination which has been

shown to occur as a result of functionalisation.⁴⁵ Characteristic lower energy emissions are a typical feature of type-II band alignment in TMD-TMD heterostructures, where the staggered alignments of the conduction and valence bands results in an observed lower energy transition.⁴⁶ Analogous, hybrid CT states between organic molecules and TMDs have been predicted to occur upon functionalization,^{17,47} where the molecular HOMO or LUMO takes on the role of a TMD band, providing energy minima across the two systems. The observed low-energy PL feature therefore provides a useful tool to probe the coupling between the PBI and MoS₂ layers with differing molecular orientation.

Fitting the 1.3-1.6 eV region of the unfunctionalized 2L MoS₂ PL spectrum, shown in Figure 3(b), resolves features at 1.48 and 1.45 eV that originate from indirect intralayer recombination with electron-hole pairs residing at the Λ - Γ and K- Γ points, here referred to as $In_{\Lambda-\Gamma}$ and $In_{K-\Gamma}$ respectively.⁴⁸ In the case of PBI-R1 and PBI-R2, together with $In_{\Lambda-\Gamma}$ and $In_{K-\Gamma}$, a broad emission band below $In_{\Lambda-\Gamma}$ and $In_{K-\Gamma}$ is present. We assign this to a spatially indirect exciton at the interface of the MoS₂ and PBI adlayer, here labelled IX_{K-PBI} . The intensity of IX_{K-PBI} differs sharply between PBI-R1 and R2, with PBI-R1 showing a much stronger contribution from IX_{K-PBI} due to the increased orbital overlap in the parallel alignment as assigned previously.

For both PBI-R1 and PBI-R2, a large increase in the B exciton intensity is observed at 2.1 eV, seen more clearly at higher incident intensities (S3, Supporting Information) and is overlaid with the perylene Raman modes observed at RT due to the overlap of the 0 \rightarrow 1 transition of the PBI molecule spectrum at 2.12 eV.²⁴ The intralayer direct emission at approximately 1.9 eV is observed in all regions and is composed of a charge neutral A exciton, A^0 , and a charged exciton (trion) contribution A^- (Figure 3(c), values for peak positions and FWHM are presented in S3, S4, Supporting Information, with further discussion). The functionalized regions show a blueshift in A^0 of 28 meV and 38 meV for PBI-R1 and PBI-R2, respectively. Regarding PBI-R1, the A emission band (A^0 and A^-) is broad at low temperatures with the main contribution being from A^- . The FWHM of the A^- peak (80 meV) is approximately twice that in 2L MoS₂ (39 eV) and higher than in PBI-R2 (57 eV) indicating increased levels of interlayer CT.⁴⁹ For PBI-R2, the A^- (1.91 eV) emission peak can clearly be distinguished from the A^0 peak (1.93 eV) with the trion binding energy being calculated to be 26 meV under low excitation power (1 μ W). The FWHM of A^0 in PBI-R2 shows a decrease of \sim 20 meV upon functionalization. The reduction in FWHM for A^0 and A^- in the PBI-R2 region together with the observed blueshift, when compared to 2L MoS₂ and PBI-R1, is possible to be a result of an increase in dielectric screening when PBI is in a perpendicular orientation and bandgap renormalization as a consequence.⁵⁰

To identify the position of the photogenerated charge carriers within the heterostructure, measurements under non resonant excitation conditions of the PBI were performed at 633 nm (S3, Supporting Information). As this is below the excitation energy of PBI, any PL features observed originate predominantly from photoexcited electron-hole pairs within the MoS₂. We observe similar indirect spectral features to the measurements at 532 nm excitation for both PBI-R1 and PBI-R2, including the presence of IX_{K-PBI} , which, together with the relative increase in trion population compared to 2L MoS₂ (Figure 3(c)), would suggest that electrons accumulate in the MoS₂ bilayer and holes are concentrated in the PBI layer. Figure 3(d) shows a graphical schematic of the band alignment in the investigated 2L MoS₂-PBI heterostructures expected following literature calculations and the observations made in the analysis of the PL spectra. End group functionalization has been shown to have a minimal influence on the calculated HOMO and LUMO of PBI derivatives in most cases, giving ionization potentials (HOMO) of -5.9 to -6.0 eV and electron affinities (LUMO) of -3.6 to -3.5 eV for similar molecules, relative to the vacuum

energy.⁵¹ For 2L MoS₂, an ionization potential and electron affinity (i.e. valance band maximum (VBM) and conduction band minimum (CBM)) of -6.0 and -4.1 eV is expected respectively, based on GW calculations.⁵² This would result in the type-II alignment observed here with a slight offset between the MoS₂ VBM at the Γ -point and PBI HOMO leading to the spectral features that can be observed here.

Photoluminescence Power Dependency

Figure 4 Power dependency of PL intensity for (a) Momentum direct, and (b) Momentum indirect transitions for 2L MoS₂, PBI-R1 and PBI-R2. Graphs include power law fits of intensity (I) as a function of power (P) and the calculated exponents of the respective data. i) and ii) for PBI-R2 denote separate fits for low and high-power regimes.

To gain further insight into the mechanisms of exciton generation and recombination between the two regions, the dependence of PL intensity I to laser excitation power P was measured which follows a power law relationship, $I \propto P^x$.⁵³ By analyzing the power dependency of the direct A and indirect emissions for 2L MoS₂ over a range of excitation powers (10^{-1} - 10^3 μ W, including the low power regime discussed above, measured at low T) on a log-log scale (Figure 4(a),(b)), all spectral features follow a near linear relationship with increasing power. The power law exponent close to 1 indicates monomolecular recombination for all direct transitions over broad range of incident power, as trion emission in this case is limited by hole population (Figure 4(a)). This is expected for MoS₂ deposited onto SiO₂ due to high levels of n-doping from the substrate which agrees well with the high intensity of the A⁻ trion emission shown in Figure 2(d). Both momentum indirect transitions within 2L MoS₂ originating from a hole at the Γ point and

an electron either at the K-point or Λ -point have almost identical power dependence, giving a nearly power independent transition probability for these indirect features (Figure 4(b)).

Regarding the functionalized regions, the fitted exponents of the momentum indirect recombination intensities for all transitions and structures remains sublinear (Figure 4(b)) where $I_{\Lambda-\Gamma}$ is suppressed to the greatest degree upon functionalisation, particularly at higher excitation powers. For PBI-R1, fitting of the direct A^0 and A^- transitions again indicates monomolecular recombination with an exponent close to 1 (Figure 4(a)). The interlayer exciton between an electron at the MoS₂ K valley and a hole at the PBI HOMO level is obviously only observable for the functionalized samples PBI-R1 and PBI-R2. In the low power regime ($10^0 - 10^2 \mu\text{W}$), the momentum indirect intralayer excitons show similar trend in the power dependent PL intensities as the interlayer excitons $I_{X_{K-PBI}}$ for both types of heterostructure. At higher excitation powers, $I_{X_{K-PBI}}$ shows a stronger nonlinearity, hence a stronger reduction in intensity when compared to $I_{K-\Gamma}$. We interpret this to be due to a saturation of states due to the reduced orbital coupling between the systems.

For PBI-R2, a similar linear relationship is seen for A^0 and A^- up to 100 μW (Figure 4(a)). The trion/exciton ratio, A^-/A^0 , shows an increase in this region for both PBI-R1 and PBI-R2 compared to 2L MoS₂, from 1.2 to approximately 4.2 and 1.8 for PBI-R1 and R2 respectively (S5, Supporting Information). We assign this to a reduction in relative hole population in MoS₂ in PBI-R1 due to CT between the PBI and MoS₂, giving rise to a higher trion population.⁵⁴ This trend deviates in PBI-R2 under higher excitation intensities with a sharp increase of the A^-/A^0 ratio, at the same point as the reduction in indirect PL intensity discussed previously. This indicates a saturation in indirect recombination in the heterostructure where we propose the following mechanism:⁵⁵ Based on the observations discussed above, this inflection point signifies a limit on the interlayer hole transfer from MoS₂ to PBI due to the poor interfacial orbital overlap, effectively changing the donor-acceptor ratio due to a saturation of filled states.⁵³ The large increase in trion density within the MoS₂ would indicate that electron transfer from the PBI molecule continues, due to a continuum of accepting states at higher levels of the MoS₂ conduction band available for electron transfer, whereas for hole transfer to PBI, the acceptor HOMO is localized and more sensitive to alignment. This increase in trion intensity is accompanied by a redshift in the peak energy of $I_{X_{K-PBI}}$ (S5, Supporting Information). Characteristically in TMD-TMD heterostructures, higher IL exciton populations result in a blueshift of the emission energy with increasing excitation power due to repulsive interactions between static out-of-plane IL excitonic dipoles.⁵⁶ As this is not observed for PBI-R1 in the power range investigated here, it is possible that this redshift comes from screening due to the increased electron population in the MoS₂ layer, however the exact mechanism warrants further investigation.

Conclusions

In this work, we report on the modulation of the optical emission properties of 2L MoS₂ upon noncovalent functionalisation with a PBI monolayer, forming an organic-inorganic heterostructure. Domains with different orientations of PBI have been identified using in-depth Raman spectroscopic characterization. The regions extent over several micrometers show distinctly different properties. Perylene orientation-dependent PL quenching at room temperature is observed, which we have attributed to different levels of CT efficiency in type-II alignment, and nonradiative recombination. We observe increased strain in the MoS₂ lattice in areas of high orbital alignment of the PBI molecules with the MoS₂ lattice. At low temperatures, PL measurements show the emergence and stabilization of IL excitons between the organic and inorganic layers. The intensity of these indirect emission signatures

show dependence on the molecular orientation of the perylene film and orbital overlap with MoS₂ and excitation power. We find that under high excitation power, CT becomes saturated in the case where the PBI molecules have reduced orbital overlap with the surface, leading to increased trion densities. Notably, RT Raman mapping already allows for rapid and simple evaluation of the molecular alignment and organic layer coupling. The study has implications for both fundamental understanding of the spectroscopy of these materials, the control of photogeneration of charge carriers in these systems, and for optoelectronic devices based on 2D organic-inorganic heterostructures.

Methods:

Two-dimensional MoS₂ flakes were produced by mechanical cleavage of bulk crystals (HQ Graphene) onto 70 nm thermally grown SiO₂/Si substrates using Nitto tape. The substrate thickness was chosen in order to increase the optical contrast of the MoS₂ to aid the identification of thinned layers.⁵⁷ The MoS₂ flakes were first characterized at room temperature without any chemical treatment, and then selectively functionalized with N-(1-pentylhexyl)-N'-(3,6,9,12-tetraoxatridecyl)perylene-3,4:9,10-bisimide (PBI) using wet chemical deposition. Similar to methods described previously,²² the sample was immersed into a 0.1 mM PBI solution in THF for 16 hours. The functionalized material was then repeatedly washed in THF and IPA before drying under nitrogen. The freshly cleaved samples were functionalized in the same manner but were not subjected to characterization before PBI deposition, to limit the exposure of the MoS₂ surface to ambient adsorbates.

All RT optical measurements were carried out at 21°C on a WITec Alpha300 R Raman microscope (Oxford Instruments) with a temperature-controlled stage (Linkham THMS 600). RT PL and Raman measurements were performed with a 532 nm laser line using either a 600 or 1800 g/cm diffraction grating. Component analysis and extraction was carried out using multivariate analysis in WITec Project FIVE software. AFM imaging was performed using a Jupiter XR microscope (Asylum, Oxford Instruments) operating in AC mode with an AC-240TS-R3 cantilever. The AFM images were processed using Gwyddion 2.60. Additional aggregates are found over the entire surface of the heterostructure due to crystallization from the PBI solution but could not be removed by further washing of the surface. Signals from these aggregates could not be detected in the optical measurements and mapping discussed above so can be seen to be decoupled from the MoS₂ surface in this regard and subtracted from the line profile.

For low temperature measurements, the samples were cooled to 4K in a Bluefors dilution refrigerator with optical access. The samples were excited using either 532 nm or 632 nm wavelength lasers. PL and Raman spectroscopy was performed using a home-built setup consisting of a triple grating spectrometer in a subtractive mode coupled to a liquid Nitrogen cooled CCD. In case of PL measurements, the gratings used were 300 g/mm, 300 g/mm and 600 g/mm for the three spectrometer stages respectively. For Raman measurements, 2400 g/mm gratings were used for all the three spectrometer stages. For circular polarization resolved measurements, quarter waveplates of appropriate wavelength range were introduced in both the excitation and detection paths. All PL spectra were fitted with Lorentzian functions.

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